

THEORETICAL BASICS IN STUDYING THE PROBLEM OF AGGRESSION

Tojiboyeva Gulkhumor Rakhmonjonovna
Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD),
associate professor

Israilov Akromjon is the son of Ikromjon
Andijan State University Pedagogy-psychology
4th level student

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ANNOTATION. This article covers the researches of eastern thinkers and western psychology aimed at studying the problem of aggression, which is one of the manifestations of behavioral deviation that occurs during adolescence. Basically, in our article, a number of thoughts, ideas and theories aimed at studying the problem of aggression have been adequately discussed.

KEY WORDS. Aggression, pedagogue, psychologist, aggression, upbringing, cognitive, eros, thanatos, instinct, evolution, phylogenetic and ontogenetic, stress, destructiveness, instinctivism, behaviorism, frustration.

INTRODUCTION. As we think about solving the complex and important issues that the rapidly changing life is putting before us today, we are sure that the solution should be formed by education and upbringing of young people.

Adolescent aggression is one of the acute problems not only for pedagogues and psychologists, but also for the whole society. The socio-economic conditions of human life, the high rhythm of life, the density of cities, and the increasing number of information media have an impact on the mental state of people. The growing trend of juvenile delinquency and the increase in the number of children prone to an aggressive form of morality have put forward the study of the psychological conditions that provoke such dangerous manifestations as a task of first-class importance. For this reason, studying aggression and aggressive behavior in adolescents and their elimination is the main urgent issue.

The increase in aggressive children is the need to develop effective methods of working with them. It consists in studying the phenomenon of aggression, the characteristics of the manifestation of adolescent aggression and the possibilities of its elimination.

Honorable **President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev** has such words: "**We will certainly build a new Uzbekistan together with the youth.**"[1]

Currently, these words serve as a programmatic action, that is, educating young people who are mature and mature in all aspects, physically strong, mentally healthy, who can compete with their peers in the world in every way is the demand of the present time. That is why it is an urgent issue of today and the future to educate young people who have received education and upbringing, who have formed spiritual and educational characteristics, to study and eliminate negative defects in their behavior.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. The wisdom of Eastern scholars, including Ibn Sina, Nizamulmulk's "Politics", Nasir Khysrav's "Saodatnama", "Roshnoyinoma", Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Kutadgu Bilig", Mahmud Koshgari's "Devonu Lug'otit Turk", Ahmad Yugnaki's Attention to child education is reflected in works such as "Hibat ul-haqaiq", wisdom of Abu Rayhan Beruni,

"Nightmare" by Kaikovus, "Mahbub ul-Qulub" by Alisher Navoi, "Akhlaqi mohsini" by Husayn Vaiz Koshifi. .

From the mentioned works, it is possible to come to a general conclusion that if a child is the happiness of parents, education is the child's today, tomorrow and future. That is why education is a social phenomenon.

Education has existed since the beginning of human society. After all, in order for a person to be the most perfect species on earth, he must first be educated. There is a saying among our people that "A teacher must first of all be educated". The thinker Ibn Sina said to educators, "Whatever advice you give to someone, first of all follow it yourself."

In raising children, expanding their spiritual outlook and It is the duty of all of us to use the opinions, advices and wisdom of thinkers for enrichment and to raise a mature person.

A person is a separate individual, essentially a whole socio-moral world. It embodies the human essence, its value as an existence. The person is interpreted differently in social and humanitarian sciences from the point of view of his direction, research object and purpose.

All currently available theories of aggression, with their diversity, can be divided into four main categories, taking into account aggression:[12]

- Innate motivation or deposit - attraction theory (Z.Freud, K. Lorentz);
- Need activated by external stimuli - frustration theories (J.Dollard, L. Berkowitz);
- Cognitive and emotional processes - cognitive theories (L. Berkowitz, Silmann);
- Social - current view of the theory of social education (A. Bandura).

The first category of theories, despite the diversity of approaches, stems from the fact that aggression is considered by its supporters as an innate instinctive form of behavior. In other words, aggression manifests itself because it is genetically programmed. Therefore, any, even the most positive, changes cannot prevent the manifestation of the social environment. Most likely, it weakens it. And, of course, there is some truth here.

Z.Freud's "Theory of Aggression as a Purposeful Instinct". Freud paid little attention to the phenomenon of aggression, considering sexuality (libido) and the instinct of self-preservation as the main and dominant forces in man. From this point of view, aggression was seen simply as a reaction to the blocking or elimination of libidinal impulses. Aggression is neither seen as an integral part of life nor as a permanent and inevitable part.

However, in the 20s, he completely abandons this concept. In "I and He", as well as in all his later works, he puts forward a new dichotomous pair: the desire for life (eros) and the desire for death (thanatos). He emphasizes that all human behavior is the result of a complex interaction of this instinct with eros, and that there is a constant tension between them.

"Ethological Approach Theory" by K. Lawrence. The evolutionary approach to the development of human aggression is primarily based on the theory of K. Lorenz, which was developed as a result of the study of animal behavior. The views of K. Lorenz are very close to the views of Z. Freud. According to the concept of K. Lawrence, aggression comes from the innate instinct of the struggle for survival. This instinct has evolved in the process of evolution and performs three important functions:[10]

1. The struggle disperses the representatives of the species over a wide geographical area, Aggression helps to improve the genetic pool of the species, because only the strongest and most energetic offspring are left.

2. Stronger animals better protect themselves and ensure the survival of their offspring.

3. The energy of aggression accumulates in the body on its own, constantly, at a constant pace, systematically over time. The more aggressive energy there is at this moment, the less force is needed for the stimulus to "shake" the aggression outward. This is called the "psycho-hydraulic model" of aggression, based on studies of animal aggression. Humans and animals usually find a source of anger in order to eliminate evil and thereby free themselves from energy tension. They claim that they do not need to passively wait for the right stimulus, they look for it themselves and even create the appropriate situations.

"Aggression Theory" by A. Basse. A. According to Bass's theory, aggression is any behavior that threatens or harms others.

Aggression refers to harming or insulting the victim

It follows from the concept that it is not obligatory to cause bodily harm to the recipient. Aggression occurs when the result of actions leads to some negative consequences. Thus, in addition to behavioral abuse, exposure to someone in a bad light, defamation or public ridicule, deprivation of necessities, and even withholding love and affection are considered aggressive under certain circumstances. can be called and, according to A.Bas, it is necessary to describe aggressive actions on the basis of three scales, i.e. physical - verbal, active - passive, direct - indirect.

"The theory of aggression as evil" by E. Fromm. In his Anatomy of Human Lethality, Erich Fromm (1994) provided a summarized analysis of various studies on human aggression. Any destructive thing in man is revised by him phylogenetically and ontogenetically as the main problem of evil at the level of the individual and society.

The phenomenon of aggression, from the point of view of E. Fromm, is the attitude of a person to the destruction of normal conditions of existence. Aggression is an "acquired property" and man is not inherently destructive. He is a victim of his history, a victim of his freedom, by which he means "a measure of responsibility"[8].

aggressiveness and destructiveness, E. Fromm combines two seemingly diametrically opposed views on the problem of aggression - instinctivism and behaviorism.

The first point of view - instinctivism - explains all the destructive things in man and reduces him to his animal essence.

The second point of view - behaviorism - puts forward the point of view that human destructiveness arises only from his social nature.

A Theory of Frustration Aggression by J. Dollard and N. Miller. Frustration is a mental state of experiencing failure due to the impossibility of meeting needs that arise when there are real or imagined insurmountable obstacles to achieving a particular goal. It can be considered as one of the forms of psychological stress. It is manifested by hopelessness, anxiety, nervousness and, finally, a feeling of hopelessness. At the same time, the efficiency of activity decreases sharply. Disappointment is accompanied by a number of negative emotions: anger, rage, guilt, etc.

The essence of J. Dollard's theory is very simple and states that frustration always leads to aggression in some form and aggression is always the result of frustration.

"Social learning theory" by A. Bandura. The theory of social learning proposed by A. Bandura is unique: here, aggression is considered as a specific social behavior, which is basically learned and maintained like many other forms of social behavior.

According to Bandura, the analysis of aggressive behavior requires consideration of three aspects:

1. ways of mastering such actions;
2. factors causing their appearance;
3. they are defined conditions.

Social learning theory believes that aggression is a social behavior that includes actions that "behind complex skills that require comprehensive learning "[5]

CONCLUSION. There are different views on the formation of aggression in the behavior of adolescents, for this reason, both in the East and in the West, they focused on the study of deviations in the behavior of adolescents. After all, youth education has always been one of the most important and urgent problems. It is still very important to study the changes in the behavior of adolescents, therefore, the study of aggressive behavior in adolescents and the acquisition of concepts about them through the above-mentioned theories serve as a theoretical basis for us.

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